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A STRUCTURAL VECTOR AUTOREGRESSIVE ANALYSIS OF THE FACTORS INFLUENCING TAX REVENUE IN CAMBODIA

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ABSTRACT

In this study we use the recursive Structural Vector Autoregression (SVAR) model to describe the short-run macroeconomic transmission mechanism in an open economy. By placing EXPORT first in the identification, it imposes contemporaneous exogeneity of external-sector innovations and pattern a hierarchy within which shocks spread through EXPORT to FX, CPI then TAX. The fact that the own-shock coefficient on EXPORT is a significant parameter clearly demonstrates the structural independence and the normalization of export innovations right, thereby justifying to consider them therefore as upstream forces of domestic macroeconomic fluctuations. The appreciation in FX rates is indicative of strong sensitivity of the exchange-rate dynamics to trade-related disturbances, which may be driven by timely currency-market responses to external demand fluctuations. The adverse impacts of EXPORT and FX on CPI implicate that short-term price dynamics are more significantly determined by external demand and cost channels than by just nominal exchange-rate pass-through. The export coefficient relative to the CPI equation is relatively large, indicating that actual trade conditions are more important than those of the commodity price index itself in affecting current-year inflation. The fiscal responses are more endogenous. TAX does not react contemporaneously to export shocks but reacts significantly to both FX and particularly CPI innovations. The very large negative CPI coefficient indicates that inflation-induced mechanisms, such as collection plus lags or dimensions of real liabilities losses are important in short-run revenue dynamics. FEVD also confirms the relevance of structural tax-specific shocks, mostly in the short-run.

KEYWORDS: Tax revenue; Foreign Exchange; Consumer Price Index; Export; SVAR Model.
JEL Classification: C32, F41, E31, H20, F31, E62.

1. INTRODUCTION

Tax revenue is the lynchpin of public finance, which offers governments financing for basic services and public goods like education, health, infrastructure and social protection. In most economies, and particularly in those with increasing demands on the budget and limited borrowing from affordable sources, boosting domestic revenue mobilization is not just a fiscal goal but a development priority. Recent conversations on revenue mobilization in Africa, for instance, highlight how losses of tax revenues due to evasion and avoidance can significantly hamper the capacity of governments to fund their development objectives and how policy and institutional changes can lead to similarly significant increases in tax collections (Traore et al., 2023).

However, for all the importance of taxation, tax performance is highly heterogeneous across countries and through time because it depends on economic structure, macroeconomic context and state capacity. Empirical analysis however indicates that tax outcomes are influenced not only by tax policy related variables like statutory rates and base definitions, but also by a host of other determinants such as the level of economic development and openness to international trade, dynamics of public debt process, governance and administrative efficiency. By analyzing European data, it is demonstrated that tax revenue collection in the long run is affected by GDP per capita, public debt, corruption control and government effectiveness (among others), taxation administration efficiency and tax rates which demonstrates that we have considered a multi-dimensional source of variability in these economy-wide indicators driving revenue performance (Anastasiou et al., 2022).

This is important as studies those that focus on developing countries, which suggest that effective tax to GDP ratios can deviate from potential revenue raised as the institutional and administrative capacity condition governments ability to translate economic activity into actual collections (Tagem & Morrissey 2023). A common theme in this literature is the role of external-sector activity, especially trade and export performance, for raising revenues. If trade can internationalize the tax base directly through border taxes, then it can also do so indirectly by raising production, profits, and consumption via export expansion. Anastasiou et al. (2022) stress the strong relationship between international trade activity (measured as imports and exports relative to GDP) with tax revenues in the European economies. Findings from studies conducted in South East Asia

have also indicated that openness may be important as has been shown by Minh Ha et al. (2022) employ panel methods for eight nations in Southeast Asia and find that trade openness is an important influence on tax revenue, particularly in their dynamic model. In the European Union, by way of example, and as a statistically significant factor Andrejovská and Glova (2023) also determine trade openness to be associated with corporate tax revenue growth, consistent with the idea that more outward-oriented economies may generate higher rates of revenue mobilization in response to broader and more observable tax bases. Regarding sub-Saharan Africa, Tagem and Morrissey (2023) find that exports and imports as ratios of GDP are among the relatively robust structural determinants included to estimate "potential" tax performance supporting the notion that trade-based variables contribute towards a characterization of the taxable capacity of an economy there.

An additional channel through which the macroeconomic may affect taxes is inflation, which has been taken into account as an approximation of macroeconomic stability. Higher inflation can lead to these negative repercussions related to real purchasing power, consumption and investment decisions – thereby weakening revenue collection conceptually. Along this line of reasoning, the study empirically articulate inflation as a discouraged option for tax revenue in that it shrink taxpayers' opportunity and willingness to comply; but their findings do not fully imply a credible result when bringing their South-East Asia sample evidence into context (Minh Ha et al., 2022). Evidence from EU corporate taxation, however, suggests the underlying relation is much more complex. An estimate from the panel suggests that inflation (measured with a collection-adjusted consumer price index) is positively related to corporate tax revenues, which has shown how inflation's net impact could rely on country environment and type of tax system as well as how fast tax systems and nominal bases responds to changes in prices (Andrejovská & Glova, 2023).

Foreign exchange conditions typically captured by the external value of the currency (domestic currency units per US Dollar), offers a macroeconomic dimension that may be particularly important in cases where taxable activity is closely linked to trade and imported inputs. Movements in the exchange rate can affect the domestic-currency value of imports and exports, influence inflation, and influence the profitability of export-oriented sectors with implications for changes in tax bases for

consumption taxes, trade taxes, and income-based taxes. Although certain determinant frameworks acknowledge exchange-rate regimes as components of the macro-policy environment that affect revenue outcomes, direct empirical scrutiny of exchange-rate effects does not generally receive the same degree of attention as do trade and institutional variables. For example, an article focuses on exchange rates and inflation within the wider array of government-policy and macroeconomic factors that could affect revenue performance, whilst its own findings emphasize developmental-indicator debt service and governance-specific determinants. This presents a potential important direction of future work. Conditions of the exchange rate may matter primarily as they interact with trade exposure, inflation and administrative capacity, but their independent effect on revenue performance is much less clear in comparative empirical settings (Anastasiou et al., 2022).

In addition, institutional and administrative influences may mitigate the influence of macroeconomic factors on tax revenue. Studies on sub-Saharan Africa demonstrate that capacity to tax is strongly related to institutional dimensions, including the even distribution of public goods (positive), and political corruption (negative)—which supports the argument that taxpayer compliance hinges upon trust and fairness (Tagem & Morrissey, 2023). Traore et al. (2023) find evidence that international cooperation mechanisms in the form of cross-border information sharing for tax purposes are associated with higher tax revenues in African countries, which is consistent with better enforcement curtailing evasion possibilities. These results support a fundamental conclusion of macroeconomic work on revenue: there may be different sources of revenue from the same inflation (or trade or exchange rate) shock, depending on governance quality and compliance behavior and the efficiency with which tax is collected.

As it has been stressed out in empirical literature, the performance of tax systems is depending on wider macroeconomic preconditions and structural determinants (Đurović Todorović et al., 2024). But while taxation clearly lies at the heart of economic governance, the influences on tax revenue are still debated today, especially in emerging and developing countries which persistently find it difficult to mobilize revenue. Furthermore, in the era of globalization and digitalization revenue mobilization has become more complex with concerns being raised about tax base erosion, capital flight and changes in the composition of taxable

activities. These developments have rendered the question how foreign macroeconomic conditions influenced domestic tax revenues, including exchange rate movements, (inflation-induced) price changes abroad and export performance ever more urgent (Hanappi et al., 2024). In addition to international trade and investment flows, the shadow economy and institutional arrangements, create further troubles for tax performance. Evidence shows that as the economy becomes more informal tax collection falls and the structure of fiscal policy changes, in particular by passing from direct to indirect taxes (Dokas et al., 2024). Similarly, institutional quality as well mediates the effects of government revenue on economic growth, reaffirming the significance of macroeconomic stability and good governance for generating revenue (Ayana et al., 2024).

As highlighted by some recent empirical research findings, the performance of tax revenue is not a fiscal phenomenon per se, but rather an expression of general economic development and institutional effectiveness. In addition, economic growth, trade openness, industrial value added, inflation rate, unemployment and public debt are often indicated as main explanatory variables. Of these, the macroeconomic stability indicators—particularly inflation and exchange rate behavior—are key in conditioning the tax base and determining revenue mobilization ability. Inflation can undercut purchasing power, distort consumption and investment behavior, and lower real tax receipts (Ristić Cakić et al., 2025).

Another study emphasizes that tax revenue dynamics are also naturally complicated by macroeconomic volatility and uncertainty. In addition to macroeconomic variables, economic policy uncertainty affects not only economic growth but also tax performance by changing investment, consumption and compliance behavior (Sakar et al., 2025). Growing uncertainty could act as a drag on economic activity, squeezing the tax base and undermining fiscal stability. In addition, financial development has been seen as a channel through which tax revenue would be mobilized through the formalization of the economy and reduction in shadow activities (Kamasa et al., 2025). This is especially the case in open economies, where foreign exchange rate is crucial. Volatility in exchange rate can affect inflationary pressures, import prices and export competitiveness that in turn may have implications for direct and indirect tax receipts. And export performance means an expansion of the tax base with increased corporate profits, employment

and value added creation as well as trade-related tax revenue (Fambeu, 2025).

Although the existing literature examines macroeconomic determinants, financial development avenues or policy uncertainty effects on tax collections, very few papers consider specifically the joint impact of external sector variables (foreign exchange and exports) and price stability (inflation), directly or indirectly, on tax revenue outcomes. This is a significant omission; especially in light of the increasing globalization and currency volatility, and inflation in recent decades. The objective of this paper is to determine whether certain macroeconomic variables (foreign exchange rate, inflation rate and export performance) have a statistically significant impact on tax revenues. In concentrating on these macroeconomic parameters, the paper seeks to make three contributions to the literature. One, it analyses price stability, external sector performance and fiscal outcomes together. Second, it enhances understanding of the way macroeconomic instability impacts on public revenue mobilization. Third, it provides policy-relevant messages on the macroeconomic configuration that would enhance the fiscal sustainability.

It is essential to note the relationships between exchange rate, inflation rate, export and tax revenue for policymakers. Therefore, if exchange rate volatility and/or inflation could significantly influence tax revenue in the past for instance and considering export performance were important for fiscal balance; stability of macroeconomic environment aiming competitiveness in turmoil time on external sector would be an issue not only for growth purpose but also against fiscal vulnerabilities. Accordingly, this paper counterfactually assesses the contribution of movements in the foreign exchange rate, changes in inflation acceleration and deceleration as well as export performance on tax revenue with the aim of providing empirical information for macroeconomic policy formulation as well as broadening the understanding of tax elasticity.

This paper is organized based on five sections. Section 1 is an introduction. This section describes the research background of the study, setting out its research problem and objectives. Section 2 includes the literature review that introduces the discussion and evidence of previous work. Section 3 explains the econometric model and data collection and analysis. Finally, Section 4 gives the empirical results, and Section 5 concludes with policy implications.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

As proposed by Richardson (2006), tax revenue could be expressed as a function of the effective tax base and compliance and administrative capacity, on the one hand, macro-structural drivers that increase or reduce taxable activity on the other. Richardson estimates cross-national tax evasion and finds that the non-economic determinants generally crowd out the effects of fiscal deterrence, with both system-level—in particular, lack of complexity—and individual factors—higher level of general education's, tax morale perceived fairness, and greater involvement in services-based income sources—strongly linked to less evasion more revenue actually collectible given a statutory fiscal regime.

Trade-focused studies also differ in conclusion over whether opening up increases revenues through growth and lower border tax burdens or decreases them from the effects of tariff reductions and the limited extent to which other types of taxes are replaced domestically. In a research shift, export upgrading rather than liberalization has come into focus, and export diversification and improving the quality of exports tend to increase non-resource tax revenues in the short and long run across countries to varying degrees for low-income economies. Positive channels entail more earnings, wages, consumption and import-based tax bases; and negative channels include restricted enforceability over new businesses and unsatisfactory tariff revenues under liberalization (Gnangnon & Brun, 2017).

Efficient factor-income tax combinations influence employment, innovation, growth, and so also the tax base. Transferring the burden between labor and capital can also increase employment at a cost of reduction in growth; the welfare effects and revenues from changes in labor taxations critically depend on innovation externalities, as well as government-finance requirements (Long & Pelloni, 2017). Looking at MENA panel estimates, a study finds a negative relation between trade openness and government revenue, which is explained by the dependence on trade taxes and imperfect substitution towards domestic taxation; in addition, it finds positive relations with higher GDP per capita and lower corruption (Shubati & Warrad, 2018).

A global contribution is the stochastic frontier approach that models the country's tax potential as an unobservable parameter of a production function and defines it as its maximum feasible value, given structure of economy and institutions, while tax effort is defined as a ratio between actual collections

and the estimate of maximal level. Applying new harmonized cross-country revenue data and stochastic frontier methodology, it was found that increased income levels, non-agricultural size, openness to trade exposure, investment in human capital accumulation, financial deepening and stability (low inflation), urbanization as well as reduced corruption are related to operating near the tax frontier. Tax effort is well below potential on average, indicating a substantial gap that is not explained by tax rates but rather reflects inefficiencies of collection and governance (Mawejje & Sebudde, 2019).

A parallel literature has a financial development and inclusion approach as tools to expand the taxable base and attack informality. Cross-country panel evidence connects greater financial inclusion, for instance, account ownership, to the levels of tax revenues and taxes in various categories (corporate, income and direct taxes). The underlying channel is that formal access adds to the traceability of transactions, boosts reported incomes in the long-run, and can decrease shadow economics activity and may expand the base without only statutory rate changes (Oz-Yalaman, 2019).

Macroeconomic conditions also bear on collections, via valuation effects and tax base volatility. Cross sectional evidence for Kenya indicate a mixed regime with varying competitive pressures on the tax bases but also trade-offs when real exchange rate volatility may transmit into import volumes, domestic prices and effective tax bases with net implications depending on import compression versus valuation of taxable imports as well as the underlying inflation environment (Rutto, 2020). More broadly, cross-country estimates indicate that non-resource tax revenue instability depresses the non-resource tax share of GDP, more so when public expenditure instability, growth volatility, inflation volatility and terms-of-trade volatility are higher. This makes revenue instability, in its own right, a factor because unstable revenues militate expenditure planning and can undermine the investments that are usually necessary to enhance collections (Gnangnon, 2021). Country-specific and structural models confirm the role of growth, openness, fiscal stance, and external financing. Evidence on Jordan from ARDL approach shows a positive relationship between per capita income and government expenditures with tax revenues, as well as negative effect of foreign aid, which in line with the argument that aid may lessen the motivations for domestic revenue effort (Qudah, 2021).

Tax institutions – how well people pay taxes and

the magnitude of tax evasion – have become key to understanding variation in revenue yields. Experience from Indonesia suggests that extensive evasion can lead to a rapid erosion of the revenue floor and strong developments in financial sector development can only partially offset the losses. These limitations notwithstanding, the relationship between financial development and evasion is not meaningless: greater participation in financial markets and more extensive credit penetration (e.g., that which attenuates informal sector activity) also correlate positively with evasion levels. In combination, these results show how better governance and increased financial transparency can influence the capacity of a country to mobilize revenue (Safuan et al 2022). Drawing on data for Spain, a different study finds that both tax revenue and public spending influence output in the short and long term, but the magnitude and direction of these effects are not uniform across periods when fiscal policy is tightening or easing. The findings suggest, in this regard, that unjustified higher taxes depress economic activities and erode lower future revenue performance while well-designed fiscal consolidations promote growth-maintaining stability (Sosvilla-Rivero & Rubio-Guerrero, 2022).

It is widely assumed that economic growth plays a significant role of determining the extent to which taxes can be mobilized, owing to its impact in increasing both income and output, this contributes to provide a larger tax base and as consequence, more amount of resources in collecting revenue. This is also supported by the evidence in the Baltic countries where municipalities also show that they have a positive significant effect of GDP per capita on tax revenues, so higher income levels and therefore larger fiscal capacity, as it originally would expect for more developed economies. Trade openness and industry value added is also positive as the tax base broadens and level of transaction increases. Higher government spending usually means higher taxes, due to the greater activity in the economy and more taxable revenue. In contrast, higher public debt and macroeconomic instability such as inflation and exchange rate fluctuations worsen the collection of taxes because there is a lack of investor trust, passive business activities and disloyalty (Mirović et al., 2003).

Sectoral structure also affects the outcomes of tax revenues. The move away from an agricultural to nonagricultural economy is usually believed to benefit revenue collection due to the perceived ease of taxing the formal sector. Evidence from Tanzania suggests that growth of services has a strong positive

impact on tax revenues, particularly government services and tradable output processing which can be more easily monitored by the tax body. This finding is in line with the argument that structural transformation towards services can help to expand tax bases in LDCs (Mapunda et al., 2023). Another important factor which determines government revenue is FDI, however and mixture results are obtained on its effect in theoretical studies. The FDI can lead to economic expansion, employment generation, and profits of corporations to expand; however, measures taken by the government such as aggressive tax breaks and round tripping provisions might end saving taxes. The results of time series for South Africa indicate that FDI significantly in the long run reduces tax revenue, suggesting that favorable effects coming from investment inflows can possibly be undermined by the use of tax holidays and aggressive policy to attract international investment. These findings show that the co-integration in FDI and tax revenue have made its conduct of creating a conducive investment space with wise policy to be an uphill task. Fostering the financial sector could also facilitate tax mobilization, in so far as it helps formalize transactions and tax collection. The tracking systems on income and consumption will be enhanced which may lead to high tax compliance and efficiency of tax collection especially in developing countries that are leaning towards financial inclusion (Jemiluyiand & Jeke, 2023).

More interestingly, the empirical results of Taiwan suggest that the relationship between economic growth and tax revenue is an inverted U form; both total tax revenue and direct tax revenue follow a N-shaped curve cruise with GDP as taxation leads to erosion of the tax base at higher level of taxes. The explanation is the burden of effective packaged taxes increases, and informal sector expands beyond threshold levels of the tax load. Second, indirect taxes exhibit a negative or weak positive affect on economic growth in the presence of improved compliance and narrowed evasion space (Wang, 2022). Segmentation and diversity of sources of revenue are also crucial for the sustainability of tax revenues. The structure and diversification of sources are not unimportant in the sustainability of tax revenues, either. Evidence from Indian states also indicates that high reliance on few taxes, particularly sales tax, leads to greater volatility of revenue and impairs fiscal stability (Darshini & Gayithri, 2023).

In Lithuania, it is observed that in both short and long run economic growth raises tax receipts with the

former being more pronounced for corporate taxes and indirect taxes due to rectification of individual's paying capacity as well local but surrounding the shadow economy discounting station (Ulvidiené et al., 2023). Tax revenue mobilizations are also macro stability-wise sensitive. Inflation and fiscal disequilibria erode real tax revenues, because of inefficient collection lags, non-respective laws. Moreover, exchange rate movements and external sector behavior also affect tax revenues significantly in trade dependent economies with consumption taxes (Garg et al., 2024). More in addition, as regards to the fiscal exchange theory and resource bargaining theories, an empirical evidence from sub-Saharan African setting reveals that pro-poor growth indeed has a sizeable and statistically significant positive impact on tax revenue mobilization by increasing taxpayer's compliance or broadening the tax base (Adeosun et al., 2024). By contrast, for resource-dependent economies, revenue instability is largely caused by volatility of commodity prices and highlights the crucial importance of diversified sources of revenues and viable non-oil tax bases (Kutu & Ohanba, 2024). Furthermore, FDI and openness of trade have an opposite relationship with tax revenue for which feeble institutional capacity would allow profit shifting and erode the tax base (Omodero & Yado, 2024).

Substantial consideration has also been given to monetary and financial conditions as key revenue drivers. A few findings from Sub-Saharan Africa indicate that there may be some indirect influence on the tax base through monetary policy transmission, via private sector credit and liquidity conditions. The poor supply of private credit restrains business growth and reduces taxable income, subsequently affecting revenue (Omodero, 2024). The contribution of external financial flows to the variation in realized tax revenue is also relevant. Remittances and their fiscal effects probably to a greater extent than in any other sphere of public finance, it is possible to observe indirect tax revenue effects remittances are having on the finances of post-socialist countries. Household consumption funded by remittances expands the indirect tax base, and a rise in entrepreneurship, though only minimally taxed (Vusal Zohrab, 2024), supports direct taxes. Institutional strength therefore appears to be both an immediate covariate of revenue performance, and a conditioning variable shaping the effects on growth and effectiveness of revenue efforts. There is some evidence from sub-Saharan Africa that the inherent adverse relationship between government revenue, proxied by tax ratio to GDP, and growth weakens on

interaction with stronger institutional quality - measured in broad terms as rule of law, government size, regulatory efficiency and market openness. This interaction effect would suggest that same sized increases in revenues may lead to different macroeconomic effects depending on the institutional setting, and therefore continued revenue performance depends upon credibility, administrative capacity and rent-seeking constraints (Ayana et al., 2024).

Analysis of the WAEMU countries reveals that current expenditure, debt service and security outlays expansion have a negative impact on fiscal space and this limits government's ability to raise additional tax revenues. Expanding the tax base and including undertaxed sectors, agriculture for instance, into the formal tax net are similarly acknowledged to be critical in enhancing revenue robustness (Dao et al., 2025). Moreover, the tax effort is harmed by macroeconomic instability. Empirical evidences from East African countries also suggest that exchange rate volatility has a negative and significant long-run effect on government tax revenue expenditure as a consequence of the spirit down of investment and positively affect economic efficiency and consumption based tax bases (Fisseha, 2025). Findings within the Azerbaijani framework also claim that use of digital tax design and automation, targeted reforms, technology utilization are channels to elicit efficient revenue collection in short as well as long term while large swerves in legislations plant the ambiguity related legislations seed and it dispossesses the future prospects for obtaining within-border efficiency in terms of revenue generation (Gazanfarli & Zhelev, 2025).

At firm level, the results for Nigeria show that

A common SVAR model in contemporaneous form is formulated as follows:

$$A_0 y_t = \alpha + \sum_{i=1}^p A_i y_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

Where $y_t = [EXPORT_t \quad FX_t \quad CPI_t \quad TAX_t]'$ is the 4×1 vector of endogenous variables, with $A_0 \in \mathbb{R}^{4 \times 4}$ nonsingular, $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}^{4 \times 1}$, $A_i \in \mathbb{R}^{4 \times 4}$, and the structural shocks are $\varepsilon_t \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I_4)$. Equation (1) can be arranged as follows for $\varepsilon_t(\theta_S)$:

$$\varepsilon_t(\theta_S) = A_0 y_t - \alpha - \sum_{i=1}^p A_i y_{t-i} \quad (2)$$

The structural innovations in Equation (2) implies by parameters $\theta_S = \{A_0, \alpha, A_1, \dots, A_p\}$.

This implies the reduced-form mapping

$$y_t = a + \sum_{i=1}^p \Phi_i y_{t-i} + u_t, \quad \text{with } a = A_0^{-1} \alpha, \Phi_i = A_0^{-1} A_i, u_t = A_0^{-1} \varepsilon_t$$

and therefore,

$$\Sigma_u = \mathbb{E}[u_t u_t'] = A_0^{-1} (A_0^{-1})'.$$

domestic currency broad money and credit availability stimulate corporate tax revenue by fostering business growth, whereas high lending rate and exchange rate volatility discourage the tax base, as well as reduce efficiency of tax administration. Moreover, tax effort is conditioned by institutional and structural factors. The instantaneous reforms in the administration of tax together with merit based tax policy and rigid financial regulation results to an excess revenue productivity by minimizing evasion and promoting compliance while constant changes in legislation militate against revenue efficiency (Omodero & Yado, 2025). Confirmatory evidence from Sub-Saharan Africa indicates that inflation and FDI exert both short- and long-run mixed effects on tax revenue, while trade openness and per capita income augment the capacity of the revenue only in specific macroeconomic stability environments (Omodero, 2025). That is, more provocatively, that political uncertainty is also a constraint of tax collection. For instance, the actual information of Türkiye clearly showed that economic policy uncertainty has a notable impact to decrease tax revenues and this indirectly hampers investment decision; take prohibitive action and simulations and acts to prevent taxes while discouraging production activities. Uncertainty results in tax revenue fall, both directly through compliance decrease and indirectly, by decreasing consumption, employment and corporate profitability (Tazegül et al., 2025).

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Model Specification

Because $\varepsilon_t \sim \mathcal{N}(0, I_4)$, the conditional density of y_t given lags has Jacobian $|\det(A_0)|$. Up to an additive constant, the SVAR log-likelihood is

$$\ell_S(\theta_S) = T \log |\det(A_0)| - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^T \varepsilon_t(\theta_S)' \varepsilon_t(\theta_S) \quad (3)$$

That is,

$$\ell_S(\theta_S) = T \log |\det(A_0)| - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^T (A_0 y_t - \alpha - \sum_{i=1}^p A_i y_{t-i})' (A_0 y_t - \alpha - \sum_{i=1}^p A_i y_{t-i}).$$

The MLE is defined by

$$\hat{\theta}_S = \arg \max \ell_S(\theta_S)$$

Where Θ imposes (i) $\det(A_0) \neq 0$, and (ii) enough identifying restrictions on A_0 (and/or on the shock covariance if not fixed to I_4) to make the structural parameters unique.

To form the recursive identification the endogenous variables are set in the following order:

$$(EXPORT, FX, CPI, TAX)$$

Which come up with the following contemporaneous structure, *EXPORT* is contemporaneously exogenous, *FX* responds contemporaneously to *EXPORT*, *CPI* responds contemporaneously to *EXPORT* and *FX*, *TAX* responds contemporaneously to *EXPORT*, *FX*, and *CPI*.

The estimated structure matrix is lower triangular:

$$A_0 = \begin{bmatrix} C(1) & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C(2) & C(5) & 0 & 0 \\ C(3) & C(6) & C(8) & 0 \\ C(4) & C(7) & C(9) & C(10) \end{bmatrix}$$

This recursive (Cholesky-type) structure implies a clear short-run causal hierarchy within each period.

The contemporaneous structural relationship are:

$$EXPORT_t = C(1)\varepsilon_{EXPORT}$$

$$FX_t = C(2)E_t + C(5)\varepsilon_{FX}$$

$$CPI_t = C(3)EXPORT_t + C(6)FX_t + C(8)\varepsilon_{CPI}$$

$$TAX_t = C(4)EXPORT_t + C(7)FX_t + C(9)CPI_t + C(10)\varepsilon_{TAX}$$

3.2. Data Collection and Data Analysis

This research uses monthly time series data from January 2011 to May 2025, comprising a total of 173 observations. Government tax revenues are collected from the Ministry of Economy and Finance (MEF) of Cambodia. Additionally, foreign exchange rates, which indicate the number of domestic currency units (Khmer Riel, KHR) per US dollar, along with the consumer price index and export data, are collectively sourced from the International Financial Statistics of the International Monetary Fund (IMF). For the purpose of data interpretation, all time series data in this study are transformed into natural logarithms since the first difference of logarithm data series will be interpreted as growth rate, for instance, the growth rate of tax revenue, the growth rate of FX (KHR is depreciated (positive) or appreciated

(negative)), the growth rate of CPI (inflation rate (positive) or deflation (negative)), and the growth rate of export.

The data analyzing process is initiated with graphical analysis and descriptive statistics. Next, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test will be applied to evaluate whether each data series is stationary or non-stationary. The next step is the determination of an optimal lag length of the VAR model using information criteria. In addition, the Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) technique will be applied to estimate all coefficients of the model. Of course, prior to proceeding with the analysis of impulse response functions (IRFs) and forecast error variance decomposition (FEVD), it is necessary to evaluate the stability of the model.

4. EMPIRICAL RESULTS

As indicated in Table 1, the mean of EXPORT is 1.08 and the median is 1.96, which suggests that overall export growth was positive in the sample period. The greater median indicates that some very large (negative) observations are causing the mean to decrease. Export growth rate varies between 50.99 and -40.38, indicating wide variation. With a large standard deviation of 17.42, there is significant volatility in the figure, indicating when times are good they are great but also when times turn sour, they do so quickly.

FX mean and median are -0.01 and 0.00, respectively, suggesting neutral changes and the general stability of KHR. The maximum depreciation is 1.33, while the maximum appreciation is -1.29. With a low standard deviation of 0.47, exchange rate volatility is moderated compared to export growth, and not indicative of much excess or sustained fluctuation.

CPI has an average of 0.23 and a median of 0.29, suggesting that there is positive inflation on average

though the value is not large. The max (1.60) corresponds to short to moderate inflation periods, and the min (-2.51), occasional deflation. The standard deviation, 0.55 seems to indicate moderate variability—greater than exchange rate adjustments but far less than the variance in exports or increases in tax revenue. With the mean less than the median, this means that deflationary shocks drives down the aggregate average. TAX displays the greatest volatility. So, while the mean is 0.80, the median is -0.34 meaning that most of our observations are negative despite a positive average! This discrepancy indicates that very large positive spikes increase the mean. The dispersion, which varies between 97.62 and -95.03 with a high standard deviation of 28.80 further shows significant instability, perhaps deriving from policy changes, structural reforms, the dynamics of the cycle or special fiscal events.

Table 1: Summary Statistics.

Variable	Mean	Median	Maximum	Minimum	Standard Deviation
EXPORT	1.08	1.96	50.99	-40.38	17.42
FX	-0.01	0.00	1.33	-1.29	0.47
CPI	0.23	0.29	1.60	-2.51	0.52
TAX	0.80	-0.34	97.62	-95.03	28.80

The correlation matrix between export growth, exchange rate changes, inflation and the growth of tax revenue are reported in Table 2. Correlation coefficients have values from -1 to +1, where the magnitude of r indicates the strength of the correlation, and its sign indicates the direction (positive or negative) of the relationship. Values around zero indicate weak relationships, and values near ± 1 suggest strong ones. The correlation between EXPORT and FX is 0.095, indicating an extremely weak positive association between export growth and depreciation of exchange rate (the increase values of FX are expressed in Khmer Riel per US dollar). This indicates that depreciation has a strong effect, if any, on export growth of the partner countries and also that exchange rate movements do

not show a strong direct linear relationship with exports. The correlation to EXPORT with CPI is -0.089, which suggests a very weak negative relationship between export growth and inflation. There is a small relationship between higher inflation and lower export growth, but it is tiny. Correlation of EXPORT with TAX is -0.014, which is virtually zero and indicates that there is not a significant linear association between export growth and tax receipts growth. In other relationships FX and CPI is significantly correlated (0.139) showing a weak positive relationship which corresponds with low exchange rate pass-through effect. Medium negative correlation is observed between FX and TAX with the value of -0.263. Lastly, there is a poor negative association (-0.101) between CPI and TAX.

Table 2: Correlation Matric.

Variable	EXPORT	FX	CPI	TAX
EXPORT	1			
FX	0.095	1		
CPI	-0.089	0.139	1	

TAX	-0.014	-0.263	-0.101	1
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The t-statistic of the unit root test in Table 3 indicated that EXPORT, FX, CPI and TAX have disparate non-stationarity properties at level but similar stationarity pattern at first difference. At level in Panel A of Table 3, the null hypothesis of a unit root can not be rejected for most variables, for all specifications with constant, constant and trend, and without deterministic constituents. The reported t-statistic for EXPORT and FX are much larger than the usual critical value, indicating non-stationarity. TAX is weakly significant at 10% with a constant, however, this evidence is weak and inconsistent

throughout the different specifications. Only CPI is significant at the 5 percent level, in which sample the constant and trend are included (which means there is weak trend-stationarity as constructed there). In sum, the variables considered are non-stationary in levels. In addition, in Panel B of Table 3 reveals that, after first differencing, all variables are statistically significant in most specifications. The null hypothesis of a unit root is strongly rejected at the 1% level for EXPORT, CPI and TAX, in spite that for FX also has significance up to 5%. This is to verify the stationarity of all variables at I(1).

Table 3: Unit Root Test.

Model	EXPORT	FX	CPI	TAX
Panel A: At Level				
With Constant	-1.1701	-1.5269	-1.4231	-2.6708*
With Constant & Trend	-1.9864	-1.5141	-3.6506**	-2.1504
Without Constant & Trend	8.2771	-0.4803	5.797	2.1085
Panel B: At First Difference				
With Constant	-13.6531***	-3.365**	-11.2672***	-4.4469***
With Constant & Trend	-13.6867***	-3.4154*	-11.2923***	-4.8464***
Without Constant & Trend	-2.5264**	-3.3696***	-6.5314***	-3.7752***

Note: ***, **, and * Significant at 1%, 5%, and 10%, respectively.

Table 4 summarizes the lag length selection criteria (LogL: Log-likelihood, LR: Likelihood Ratio, FPE: Final Prediction Error, AIC: Akaike Information Criterion, SC: Schwarz Criterion, and HQ: Hannan-Quinn) for VAR. These steps contribute to recipe for identifying the best lag structure and balance between goodness of fit and model parsimony. The log-likelihood also moves steadily up from -1510.80 at lag 0 to -865.03 at lag 3, which suggests better fit as more lags are incorporated. Nevertheless, improved fit is not a reason for higher lags on its own

as more parameters increase complexity. The LR test statistic is 50.48 at lag 3, so that including period t-2 substantially improves explanation over and beyond period t-1. At lag 3, the minimum value of FPE (0.57) is observed, due to which there should be less forecast error. AIC (10.79) and HQ (11.18) too have minimum values at lag 3 endorsing this specification. On the contrary, SC chooses lag 2 (11.59), with its higher penalty imposed on extra terms. Upon examining all these criteria, most clearly show that a three-lag VAR model is the appropriate specification.

Table 4: Information Criteria.

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-1510.80	NA	645.27	17.82	17.89	17.85
1	-937.65	1112.58	0.92	11.27	11.64	11.42
2	-892.36	85.79	0.65	10.92	11.59*	11.19
3	-865.03	50.48*	0.57*	10.79*	11.75	11.18*

The SVAR model was estimated by monthly data in the period from April 2011 to May 2025, which ended up covering 170 observations after calibrated. Estimation was by maximum likelihood with the

Newton-Raphson algorithm and convergence was reached after 29 iterations. The model is just identified, that is, the imposed contemporaneous restrictions are exactly what is necessary to identify

the structural parameters.

As indicated in Table 5, the structural shock coefficient on EXPORT in the EXPORT equation is $C(1)=9.2664$ ($p<0.01$), which is implicative statistically significant. Due to the fact that EXPORT is in the first, it is exogenous contemporaneously and not impacted in the same period by FX, CPI, or TAX. Furthermore, the shocks to EXPORT can thus be considered as structurally independent innovations.

Ordering EXPORT first in a recursive lower-triangular SVAR ensures a transparent short-run economic timing restriction within the model sampling frequency, innovations to contemporaneous EXPORT are not contemporaneously caused by FX, CPI or TAX. Instead EXPORT is considered the exogenous variable in the domestic block in that shocks to exports are assumed to be largely away from or determined before FX, CPI and TAX can adjust within month. This interpretation is compatible with typical open-economy reasoning, which holds that export flows tend to move in response to foreign demand conditions (foreign business-cycle shocks) and international trade-policy uncertainty, whereas domestic prices and fiscal indicators react only after a lag because of lags associated with production, shipment and contracting delays as well as administrative lags. Recent evidence from structural studies of small open economies focuses on the role of external shocks – especially global demand shocks – as drivers of domestic price and exchange rate dynamics, to lend backing for the more general case made here of treating excursions in the external sector as exogenous drivers at short horizons (Corbo & Di Casola, 2022).

The assertion that the structural shock coefficient on EXPORT is $C(1)=9.2664$ ($p <.01$) can be interpreted as follows. The structural innovation to EXPORT under the normalization, has unit variance and is orthogonal to other structural shocks. Thus, the coefficient $C(1)$ scales how the observed variable exports contemporaneously respond to a one-unit export shock and does not capture any behavioral effect of EXPORT on itself. The high statistical significance mostly means that the model predicts how large the shock's effect is scaling with this data and identification restrictions. In reporting applied SVAR, it is common to continue to check such own-shock coefficients, these are best interpreted as being part of the mapping from structural shocks to observed reduced-form innovations made rather than evidence of a causal relationship from EXPORT to EXPORT.

The view that EXPORT shocks are structurally

orthogonal can be further motivated by recent empirical evidence on trade and external uncertainty. Studies on trade policy uncertainty found that the macroeconomic effects of trade-policy news and uncertainty shocks are quantitatively important; they can alter the firms' export participation and investment decisions, undermining the view that fluctuations in exports often reflect disruptions due to changes in contemporaneous conditions such as domestic CPI or tax (Caldara et al., 2020). There is also regional evidence from Bayesian SVAR on protectionism and tariffs that tariff shocks and trade-policy uncertainty shocks have a long-lasting negative effects on trade and output, suggesting that trade-related shocks can be factored into separate structural innovations rather than being the endogenous products of domestic price-level indices or tax instruments. These findings are in line with an identification strategy where EXPORT innovations are thought of as shocks originating from shifts in global demand or foreign policy actions, global uncertainty (channels through which export orders and shipments might respond before domestic prices or fiscal variables adjust entirely) (Boer & Rieth, 2024).

The recursive assumption also has consequences for the interpretation of the larger system. With EXPORT listed first, the synchronous response of FX, CPI and TAX to export shocks allows for prompt trade-through balance of payments adjustments (exchange rate), cost and demand push factors (prices) and second round fiscal revenue collection considerations (tax). Recent SVAR analysis on exchange rate pass-through has emphasized the role of external shocks, such as global output, oil prices and global financial conditions, in the transmission to domestic prices in emerging Asia, consistent with modelling a foreign or external impulse as an upstream driver and allowing domestic variables to respond. It is specifically because identification EXPORT is contemporaneously exogenous that some short-run effect due to an external-sector shock hits in the month, and then the domestic macro and fiscal variables in lags are allowed to adjust (Beirne et al., 2024).

Contemporaneous exogeneity is an identifying assumption not an empirically verifiable truth. FX can amend to news that also affects exports very quickly and some of the pricing reaction could be in the month. Therefore, in many recent papers recursive schemes are combined with sign restrictions or explicit exogenous blocks aiming at ameliorating identification (Corbo & Di Casola, 2022; Boer et al., 2024). However, at the monthly

frequency this export-first restriction is still defensible with institutional timing such as contracting or shipping lags, administrative delay in taxing and passing through price to consumers, supporting it and lends a clean interpretation of EXPORT as the structurally independent shock that is passed through FX, CPI, and TAX dynamics.

In FX equation, the coefficient of EXPORT is positive and significantly different from zero ($C(2)=0.2476$, $p<0.01$). This shows that a positive contemporaneous surprise to EXPORT immediately raises FX. The size however implies a moderate albeit economically relevant short-run pass-through from EXPORT to FX. Moreover, the structural shock coefficient for FX is again positive and statistically significant ($C(5)=0.4645$, $p<0.01$).

In a recursive SVAR in which EXPORT is ordered before FX, the contemporaneous FX equation can be given an interpretation of how the exchange rate moves intra-month in response to an export innovation after isolating that export innovation from other structural shocks. The estimated coefficient $C(2)=0.2476$ ($p<0.01$) implies that a surprise upward shift in EXPORT causes an instantaneous increase in FX. The sign and economic interpretation of this response will depend on the exchange-rate convention in which we measure the data. As FX is expressed as KHR per dollar (up meaning depreciation), the outcome suggests that an export boom is associated with same-month depreciation, which could happen in situations where larger exports lead to an increase in domestic liquidity and import demand, more foreign-exchange market turnover or portfolio adjustments outweighing the simple forex-channel effect in the very short term.

In either quoting convention, the message is that it has a short-run mechanism through which export shocks, at high frequency, are not neutral for the exchange rate. This view is also consistent with recent open-economy SVAR evidence showing that exchange rates are very responsive to foreign, especially trade-based, shocks. For instance, in the case of small open economies Structural Bayesian VAR results indicate that global demand and external shocks are important determinants of both changes in exchange rates and prices, so that exchange rate dynamics are closely related to externally driven trade conditions (Corbo & Di Casola, 2022). Further, empirical SVAR evidence in resource and trade dependent countries brings to the fore the external shock component and exchange rate as an adjustment margin, most notably in the context of changes in trade balances, as well as

availability of foreign exchange (Chowdhury 2022).

The positive response from EXPORT to FX can also be explained by recent studies about trade-policy and global uncertainty. It has been documented that trade policy uncertainty shocks impact real activity and financial variables, and can induce fast FX movements by altering expectations about future international trade flows, risk premia and capital redistributions (Caldara et al., 2020). In such environments, a foreign demand, trade or risk sentiment news may be partially captured by export shocks that are identified in an SVAR and alter at the same time currency demand and pricing in FX markets. Since exchange rates are the forward-looking prices of assets, FX can adjust during the month when exports quantities have lags with shipments and contracting. This is in line with findings that pass-through of exchange rates and related open-economy mechanisms depend crucially on the nature of shocks and external conditions (Aisen et al., 2021).

The second reported parameter $C(5)=0.4645$ ($p<0.01$), is the FX structural model shock loading under its own equation with normalization. In a recursive SVAR, this parameter is not an economic behavioral effect; it is the scale of the impact transforming one unit of cross-equation orthogonal structural FX shock in terms of observed FX innovation. As to the significance of its weight, as a response coefficient rather than an estimated correlation, it shows that the model recognizes another exchange rate shock with non-zero (contemporaneous) impact on FX, which is ordinary in SVAR setups where exchange rates are rich of high-frequency variations and respond to several structural shocks. This view is consistent with a series of recent SVAR that consider exchange rate shocks to be key determinants of macroeconomic dynamics and of price transmission in open economies (Corbo & Di Casola, 2022; Aisen et al., 2021).

The combination of $C(2)>0$ and $C(5)>0$ aligns with an empirical narrative wherein innovations to exports induce economically significant short-run movements in FX values, while structural shocks distinct to the exchange rate continue to be a separate and precisely identified source for FX fluctuations. This finding is consistent with previous studies, which found that external demand, trade conditions and uncertainty shocks are key components of exchange rate dynamics in small open economies where the exchange rate is often treated as a fast adjustment variable when there are external shocks (Caldara et al., 2020; Chowdhury, 2022 and Corbo & Di Casola; 2022).

A negative and significant contemporaneous effects of both EXPORT ($C(3)=-0.3470$, $p<0.01$) and FX on CPI ($C(6)=-0.2288$, $p<0.05$) are found in the CPI equation. This means the contemporaneous effect of an EXPORT positive shock would be a decrease in CPI while that for FX also is to reduce CPI. The absolute size of EXPORT's impact on CPI is larger than influences from FX thereby implying that CPI is more demonstrative of movements in EXPORT. The structural shock coefficient on CPI is positive and significant ($C(8)=1.2748$, $p<0.01$).

In a recursive SVAR where EXPORT and FX lead CPI, the contemporaneous function for CPI represents the instantaneous price-level response to external-sector and exchange rate innovations after separating orthogonal structural disturbances. Point estimates suggest that EXPORT ($C(3)=-0.3470$, $p<0.01$); and FX ($C(6)=-0.2288$, $p<0.05$) cause negative and significant contemporaneous impacts on CPI. These findings suggest that a positive structural export shock lowers the CPI in the same period and likewise for a positive Exchange rate shock to the CPI contemporaneously. This higher absolute value of the export coefficient indicates that CPI is more responsive, in the short-run, to export shocks than to exchange rate disturbances.

The inverse relationship between EXPORT and CPI can also be explained from the perspective of several open-economy transmission channels. First, a more robust export performance could reflect good (externally) rather than bad (domestically-driven) demand shocks to the economy that enhance scale of output and capacity utilization. If firms work on the basis of increasing returns or if companies reap a gain from contagion in terms of productivity (learning-by-exporting), unit cost per output may decrease leading to correctional down pressure on prices at home in the short run. Second, a rise in export earnings can help improve the balance of payments situation and alleviate foreign exchange bottlenecks, which would bring down the cost of imported inputs and stabilize domestic supply conditions. In economies where import content of intermediate goods is large, such channels may have rapid pass-through to prices faced by consumers.

Based on Structural Bayesian VAR approaches for small open economies, Corbo and Di Casola (2022) uncover the fact that global demand shocks exert a strong control on domestic inflation and exchange rate movements, underlining the key role of external-sector shocks in driving price dynamics. Likewise, evidence on trade-policy uncertainty indicates that shocks to the trade sector can result in substantial macroeconomic and price adjustments and thus

contributes to supporting export-side shocks as determinants of domestic inflation. These results are consistent with a structural interpretation in which the export innovations play as upstream forces, which affect cost and demand conditions at home (Caldara et al., 2020).

The contemporaneous negative impact of FX on CPI has to be interpreted depending on the definition of the exchange-rate regime. Since FX is denominated as home currency per unit of foreign, hence an increase in FX indicates depreciation. A negative coefficient means that a depreciation shock lowers CPI in the same period. While traditional exchange-rate pass-through theory suggests that depreciation increases import prices and inflation, recent research provides evidence supporting incomplete or state contingent pass-through particularly in emerging and small open economies. In some environments, foreign-exchange rate movements reflecting better external balances or capital inflows (financing those flows) could contribute to easing of inflationary pressures along with supply expansion, policy tightening or expectations. In line with this, Beirne et al. (2024) find that the degree of exchange rate pass-through to import prices within emerging Asia depends decisively on the disturbance, as well as global factors, thereby revealing it to be a shock- and regime dependent phenomenon rather than uniform. CPI impotence According to this interpretation, adverse responses in contemporaneous CPI might suggest that short-run stabilization or demand-compression channels dominate over those from direct import prices.

The larger size of the export coefficient compared to that for the FX also suggests that, in terms of an identified pattern, CPI responds more strongly to export innovations than to exchange rate disturbances. This finding implies that the role of the (external) demand channel might be more relevant than that of the nominal exchange-rate channel in determining short-run price behavior. In related empirical research for small open economies, the dominance of global, trade-related compared to pure nominal exchange-rate shocks as drivers of inflation fluctuations is already featured. In this respect, the estimated hierarchy of effects is consistent with recent findings that global trade conditions can override domestic price setting at short horizons (Corbo & Di Casola, 2022).

The structural shock coefficients of CPI, $C(8)=1.2748$ ($p<0.01$), is the contemporaneous impact scaling of an orthogonal CPI-specific structural innovation under the normalization. This parameter

itself does not describe a behavioral elasticity; it rather maps the identified CPI standalone shock to the observed reduced form innovation. This statistical significance implies a distinct price-level disturbance that acts independently of export and exchange rate shocks. Recent SVAR often include such inflation-specific shocks, which can be interpreted as being due to domestic cost-push conditions, policy-driven innovations changes in expectations that are the result of factors other than external trade and exchange rate variations. The evidence is consistent with an interpretation in which the path of domestic inflation depends importantly on external-sector developments. Export shocks have an immediate impact on CPI than exchange-rate shocks, which is in line with recent research emphasizing the importance of global demand and trade conditions for inflation dynamics in open economies. (Caldara et al., 2020; Corbo & Di Casola, 2022).

The concurrent impact of EXPORT on TAX is not statistically significant ($C(4)=-0.3836$, $p>0.05$), indicating that there is no direct immediate transmission from EXPORT to TAX. However, FX ($C(7)=-2.4193$, $p<0.01$) has a negative and significant effect on TAX and CPI ($C(9)=-9.7960$, $p<0.01$) has very high negative significant impact on TAX. The extremely high coefficient of CPI (-9.7960) suggests that TAX reacts more to the current period than do other contemporaneous variables in response to changes in CPI. This is the strongest among all contemporaneous effects in the system. The structural shock coefficient on TAX is positive and statistically significant ($C(10)=6.9036$, $p<0.01$).

The contemporaneous tax-revenue equation in the recursive SVAR suggests that short-run fiscal developments are predominantly determined by nominal and external-price effects, rather than by contemporaneous export activity. The contemporaneous value of the coefficient estimate on EXPORT is statistically insignificant ($C(4)=-0.3836$, $p>0.05$), which means that an unanticipated export innovation does not enter tax revenue in the very same period. This finding is in line with the institutional fact that several revenue shares react to trade and output with administrative or accounting lags. Corporate income tax is settled on an annual basis and value added tax systems zero rate exports (or have export refund schemes), undermining any mechanical month outcome correlation between higher exports and net tax receipts. Evidence from across countries has also revealed that, though tax revenue and economic activity are long run elastic to the other, short run adjustments in revenues can be

dampened or lagged with respect to underlying economic movements (Cornevin et al., 2024).

In contrast, the exchange rate has an instantaneous effect on tax revenue ($C(7)=-2.4193$, $p<0.01$). The negative sign would suggest that a rise in exports leads directly to a decrease in TAX, although the appreciation versus depreciation depends on exchange rates (such as domestic currency per foreign or its inverse). Apart from the convention or inference, the estimate is consistent with a more general proposition that exchange-rate movements can quickly impinge upon fiscal performance through such flows as import values and customs bases, as well as domestic demand. Exchange-rate shocks can change the domestic-currency value of imports and imported inputs, then this affects consumption patterns and firm margins, with impacts on indirect taxes and corporate tax bases at a high frequency. Empirical studies that focus on tax performance in developing countries have observed the nexus of exchange rate dynamics and volatility, which are typically related to anemic outcomes for taxes, particularly when trade taxes and import-reliant revenue bases are salient (Ofori, 2021).

The most pronounced contemporaneous impact is the negative effect of CPI on tax revenue ($C(9)=-9.7960$, $p<0.01$). TAX is found to be highly responsive to price-level disturbances within the same period, with it dominating other contemporaneous linkages in the system. A negative CPI-TAX slope is economically coherent with the model of inflation-revenue erosion stemming from collection and refund lags, as inflation increases, the actual (real) value of tax liabilities can decrease between their first accrual and final collection. There is a growing literature that demonstrates practical policy and empirical importance of advance tax shifting as well i.e., even with nominal tax schedules increasing with prices, the timing of collection and refund processes should reduce real tax revenues during inflation episodes. This channel is especially pertinent for lagged-imposed taxes, credits/refunds, or compliance frictions and it can overshadow alternative means through which inflation increases nominal revenues, for example, fiscal drag or rising tax bases (Beer et al., 2023).

The large magnitude of the CPI effect may also be due to anemic found shocks in general equilibrium. In numerous SVAR and open-economy contexts, inflation behavior is determined by the evolution of external shocks (global demand, commodity prices, and foreign monetary conditions) that also affect domestic activity and fiscal space. Empirical evidence in small open economies has suggested that

global demand shocks (and not domestic price) play a critical role for inflation and exchange rate movements (Corbo & Di Casola, 2022). If CPI hikes reflect unfavorable supply shocks, tightening financial conditions, or demand contraction, a contemporaneous reduction in taxable transactions and profits might occur simultaneously with increasing prices causing an immediate drop in revenue. SVAR evidence for trade-policy uncertainty indicates that such uncertainty shocks lower investment and activity, thus an empirically documented channel through which price pressure or volatility raising shocks might depress near-term tax bases (Caldara et al., 2020).

At last, the positive and statistically significant structural shock coefficient of TAX ($C(10)=6.9036$, $p<0.01$), it is realized that the tax revenue has a

separate, orthogonal influence which is not contemporaneously accounted for by EXPORT, FX, or CPI as above. Structurally, it multiplies the direct impact of a one-unit tax-specific innovation under the baseline. Such innovations can credibly be viewed as mirroring developments in tax administration, compliance enforcement, policy discretion or one-time institutional events that make revenues fluctuate separately of the non-tradable sector and contemporaneous inflation and exchange-rate pressures. More recent cross-country studies of tax performance similarly emphasize that revenue performance reflects not just macroeconomic developments but also structural and institutional factors which might produce tax-relevant shocks (Apeti et al., 2023).

Table 5: Structural VAR Estimates.

Coefficient		Standard Error	z-Statistic	Probability	
C(1)	=	9.2663	0.5025	18.4391	0.0000
C(2)	=	0.2476	0.0381	6.5029	0.0000
C(3)	=	-0.3470	0.1011	-3.4318	0.0006
C(4)	=	-0.3836	0.9379	-0.4090	0.6826
C(5)	=	0.4645	0.0252	18.4391	0.0000
C(6)	=	-0.2288	0.0986	-2.3212	0.0203
C(7)	=	-2.4193	0.9285	-2.6057	0.0092
C(8)	=	1.2748	0.0691	18.4391	0.0000
C(9)	=	-9.7960	0.7501	-13.0603	0.0000
C(10)	=	6.9036	0.3744	18.4391	0.0000
Log-likelihood = -892.0806					

In terms of the recursive sequence, the structural transmission mechanism can be explained as follows. EXPORT is the most exogenous variable in the system, entering contemporaneously and pushing directly on both FX and CPI. FX is a transmission channel. It is affected by EXPORT and affects CPI and TAX. CPI reacts contemporaneously to EXPORT and FX shocks and in turn has a strong indirect effect on TAX. Last, TAX is the most endogenous variable of the system, with this variable adjusting on impact (in the same month) to innovations in all lags. Altogether, this implies that shocks spread hierarchically through the system, and there is also direct transmission going from EXPORT to CPI and from FX to TAX.

EXPORT → FX → CPI → TAX

The majority of contemporaneous coefficients are highly significant at the 1% or 5%, reflecting strong structural relationships. The only trivial coefficient is the immediate contemporaneous influence of EXPORT on TAX. Slightly more interesting is that the value of log-likelihood of -892.0806 shows good fleshiness of the estimation process. Since the model is just-identified, so the structural parameters are uniquely determined by the assumed recursive restrictions.

Figure 1: Accumulated Response to Structural VAR Innovations.

These impulse responses represent the cumulative (level) effects of one standard deviation structural shocks to *EXPORT*, the *FX*, *CPI*, and *TAX* with 95 percent confidence intervals for a 10-period horizon. The salient feature is that of strong own-shock persistence (a pervasive empirical ground in macro SVAR settings with smooth adjustment of the key nominal and external variables and where cross variable effects depend on the structural source of shocks and policy regimes (Carrière-Swallow et al., 2023)). The more discriminate cross-responses suggest that transmission through the trade, price, exchange rate and fiscal channels is present, but is not universally strong across horizons.

An *EXPORT* shock produces an immediate and persistent rise in exports, suggesting a foreign demand or competitiveness improvement that eventually goes away. The relatively small appreciation of the exchange rate and what can be viewed as some stabilization can be seen then a mild adjustment in the value of the currency to reflect improved external performance. The modest decline in *CPI* is similar to mild disinflation that occurs as external performance strengthens through channels that relax cost pressures (such as enhanced capacity utilization, tradable-goods productivity, and

reduced imported-cost pressure due to exchange-rate stability). This interpretation is also consistent with the empirical observation that inflation dynamics are frequently influenced by external and supply-side factors, and that the magnitude of the inflation response depends on both the size and persistence of an underlying shock (Ha et al., 2023).

The sharp and persistent fall of *TAX* following an export shock seems to suggest that there is some fiscal channel, depending on how *TAX* is measured. If *TAX* is indicative of a tax position but not revenue, the reaction could result from discretionary relaxation (e.g., export subsidies). If *TAX* picks up tax receipts, somehow such that so much negative response is evident, compositional or policy effects dampen the mandatory revenue rise from more trade, and in consequence an autonomous deterministic path for the fiscal variable emerges under this identification, it systematically responds to export innovations rather than being dragged by the cycle.

An *FX* shock leads to an initial increase in exports, which is followed by a negative cumulated effect. These dynamics are in a line with short cape race to the bottom that may be followed by medium-run forces mitigating the initial impetus, leading to

an overshooting type behavior in trade outcomes. Recent pass-through work highlights that *FX* movements are shock-specific. The real impact of an *FX* change vary depending on whether it is driven by monetary or financial shocks, risk premia or trade fundamentals (Carrière-Swallow et al., 2023).

The strong positive own-response of *FX* is indicative of sustained exchange-rate shocks. The low *CPI* response to *FX* shocks may reflect partial pass-through in this specification. This result is broadly in line with the fact that pass-through is frequently incomplete and dependent on macroeconomic conditions, and the fundamentals that generate exchange rate movements (Carrière-Swallow et al., 2023). Meanwhile, other evidence indicates that pass-through can be large in some countries and regimes; for instance, recent monthly evidence for Sub-Saharan Africa shows that depreciations may result in significant increases to domestic inflation (Kemoe et al., 2024). The long-term negative *TAX* response following an *FX* shock is consistent with contractionary fiscal dynamics although the actual channel of transmission differs according to whether *TAX* represents a policy tool or a revenue item.

The *CPI* shock results in a rising inflation trajectory, i.e. inflation is also found to be highly persistent. This result is in line with the results that inflation can be purely persistent if the shocks are transmitted through costs, expectations and international supply conditions (Ha et al., 2023). The time profile of *FX* increasing after a *CPI* shock is also in line with a period of external prices and nominal conditions adjusting as inflation pressures build. Its limited export response implies a modest trade reallocation from inflation shock over the horizon, which can materialize when competitiveness effects are dominated by demand, policy, and financing constraints.

A *TAX* shock generate a significant own-response that dies out and fluctuates, however, effects for *EXPORT*, *FX*, *CPI* are small and tend to be zero. Spillovers are likely if tax changes influence private-sector activities and if the tax shock is not offset rapidly by other policies. As an example of a case where the spillover might be relatively small, we can consider when tax disturbances are transitory. This is in line with evidence that fiscal shocks are not always followed by a strong positive inflation response. A recent structural analysis find, for example, a fiscal price puzzle in this context where prices fall rather than rise after some fiscal expansions (Jørgensen & Ravn, 2022). However, other studies indicate that tax shocks may have significant open-economy

implications on the current account and exchange rate (Klein & Linnemann, 2024). As such, the near-zero cross-effects in this system are most usefully thought of as an empirical characteristic of the particular identification and sample chosen, possibly reflecting policy offsets or choices of measurement for *TAX* and a world in which nominal shocks and external variables rule fiscal spillovers.

The forecast error variance decomposition (FEVD) from the four-variable SVAR is used to trace variations in export growth, exchange-rate changes, inflation and tax growth to the four structural shocks *EXPORT*, *FX*, *CPI* and *TAX* at horizons 1–10. FEVD is a traditional measure in SVAR analysis that allows measuring over time the contribution of each identified shock to the volatility of each variable, thus providing running estimates of which shocks contribute more at different horizons (Brignone & Piffer, 2025). The decomposition shows that short-run uncertainty emphasizes own shocks, but cross-variable disturbances become relevant at longer horizons, which is in line with the slow adjustment of the transmission mechanism and a delay of policy and real economy responses.

As suggested in Table 6, external-demand shocks account for the bulk of uncertainty about export growth at all horizons (78.6% at horizon 1; 61.6% by horizon 10), implying that movements in exports are predominantly influenced by disturbances arising from within the export sector. The increasing contribution of exchange-rate shocks (from 13.4% to 24.4%) provides evidence of the greater influence of macro-financial and relative price factors on export variability at medium horizons. This behavior is also in line with empirical studies that find the macroeconomic implications of exchange rate changes depend on the drivers of exchange rate movements and can operate through bilateral trade volumes as well as competitiveness over time (Carrière-Swallow et al., 2023).

The increasing role of tax shocks (2.2%–9.3%) signals an expanding role played by the fiscal channel in determining export performance which is not surprisingly as previous research found that fiscal policy can generate external-sector effects and international spillovers through both real and financial channels (Kumar et al., 2024). The modest and stable impact of the *CPI* (about 4.6–5.8%) suggests that inflation shocks are not a main source of export- growth uncertainty within this system, which is key in models where exports variability is dominated by sectoral/external sources and inflationary pressures propagate to trade activities via indirect channels.

Table 6: Variance Decomposition of EXPORT.

Period	S.E.	Shock1	Shock2	Shock3	Shock4
1	15.30535	78.60168	13.41619	5.821159	2.160974
2	16.50137	72.06053	19.25423	5.029243	3.655989
3	16.93736	69.40260	22.05490	5.026611	3.515885
4	17.23943	67.03257	22.13024	4.884375	5.952813
5	17.88433	62.73531	23.76316	4.624911	8.876618
6	17.98149	62.06119	24.49517	4.655126	8.788515
7	18.04252	61.82531	24.43690	4.716722	9.021063
8	18.07339	61.75754	24.49399	4.719364	9.029114
9	18.12506	61.66453	24.35454	4.721231	9.259700
10	18.13638	61.59086	24.42571	4.718839	9.264587

Exchange rate shocks, presented in Table 7, still account for the majority of FX variation (70.4% initially; 62.1% by horizon 10), suggesting that exchange rate disturbances are highly persistent and that there is a significant role for exchange rate-specific innovations (financial conditions, risk premia, or policy driven). Inflation shocks exhibit some degree of persistence (16–18 %), suggesting that their contribution to exchange rates are not trivial through the price–exchange-rate mechanism. This link is supportive of modern evidence on pass-through to exchange rates and the state dependence of the pass-through mechanism: the inflation effects—as well as the wider macro links—vary depending on

whether exchange rate movements reflect fundamentals or not (Carrière-Swallow et al., 2023). Empirical work for Sub-Saharan Africa also find that exchange-rate movements can be linked to significant inflation responses in certain regimes and samples, lending support for a persistent CPI-FX link (Kemoe et al., 2024). Export shocks (around 12–17%) reveal significant real-sector responses to the exchange rate, in line with open-economy adjustment where trade environments and external balance influence movements in the exchange rate. Tax shocks are still small (around 2–3 %), which implies moderate direct fiscal dominance of exchange-rate volatility in this model.

Table 7: Variance Decomposition of FX.

Period	S.E.	Shock1	Shock2	Shock3	Shock4
1	0.418563	11.65686	70.36759	16.32128	1.654268
2	0.466327	14.81265	65.09120	18.12535	1.970801
3	0.476005	14.38888	64.47074	18.46088	2.679495
4	0.484286	16.95206	62.46209	17.86925	2.716599
5	0.485302	17.03346	62.31894	17.83583	2.811768
6	0.486481	17.32777	62.07861	17.75862	2.835005
7	0.486798	17.37688	62.04110	17.74446	2.837550
8	0.487155	17.36618	62.07927	17.71876	2.835796
9	0.487275	17.35847	62.07550	17.71005	2.855981
10	0.487382	17.35173	62.08969	17.70279	2.855792

The variation of inflation significantly is induced mostly by *CPI* innovations (about 85–89%), which is in support of a high degree of persistence internal to inflation and a prominent importance of price specific disturbances in shaping uncertainty in inflation. In Table 8, the low weight placed on export shocks (around 7–12%) and *FX* shock (about 3–5%) indicate that pass-through from exchange-rate volatility to *CPI* is low in the sample used, which accords with the evidence that pass-through can be

partial and highly sensitive to the source of the movement in exchange rate movements as well as macro conditions (Carrière-Swallow et al., 2023). The small tax response implied by the low tax contribution suggests that fiscal shocks do not explain much of the variance in inflation in this system, a finding broadly consistent with SVAR evidence on how prices might respond weakly (or even not at all) to some fiscal shocks in parts of the specification space (Jørgensen & Ravn, 2022).

Table 8: Variance Decomposition of CPI.

Period	S.E.	Shock1	Shock2	Shock3	Shock4
1	0.005224	12.06487	2.547866	85.08842	0.298844
2	0.007885	10.36885	4.265308	85.06954	0.296299
3	0.010231	8.545296	4.854329	86.32927	0.271109
4	0.012227	8.141150	4.581279	87.07790	0.199673
5	0.013930	7.831409	4.033557	87.97866	0.156371
6	0.015483	7.592002	3.789187	88.49103	0.127784
7	0.016897	7.389199	3.719475	88.78314	0.108185
8	0.018185	7.347452	3.620706	88.93755	0.094292
9	0.019372	7.282970	3.506787	89.12713	0.083114
10	0.020486	7.194223	3.444738	89.28632	0.074717

Tax shocks dominate tax-growth uncertainty in the short run (95.8% at horizon 1) and continue to be the primary driver at longer horizons (72.4% by horizon 10), suggesting that fiscal dynamics are initially triggered by tax-specific innovations. The increase in export and *FX* contributions to around 12% each by horizon 10, as indicated in Table 9, suggest that fiscal dynamics are more closely linked to real activity and exchange rate conditions as the time horizon increases, which is a reflection of both real and financial channels of fiscal spillovers (Kumar et al., 2024). Open-economy evidence also indicates

that tax shocks may be accompanied by non-negligible international spillovers such as real depreciation and external-balance effects, for which the medium-run correlation of tax variability with *FX* or trade conditions would be consistent (Klein & Linnemann, 2024). The FEVD structure is therefore supportive of an interpretation that, in the near term, tax innovations dominate the level of tax volatility while macroeconomic conditions play a progressively greater role in determining fiscal outcomes as horizons lengthen.

Table 9: Variance Decomposition of TAX.

Period	S.E.	Shock1	Shock2	Shock3	Shock4
1	19.91278	3.767956	0.397980	0.012673	95.82139
2	27.12584	10.13086	9.145244	0.984047	79.73985
3	27.84014	9.728832	11.52609	2.682561	76.06252
4	28.16454	9.910945	11.26334	2.790616	76.03510
5	28.66975	11.43893	11.68661	2.878672	73.99579
6	29.09634	12.13008	11.38498	2.902546	73.58240
7	29.22845	12.06031	12.10345	2.894591	72.94165

8	29.36520	12.10846	12.16786	2.901629	72.82205
9	29.43257	12.05407	12.43403	2.888701	72.62320
10	29.49460	12.10234	12.54687	2.905566	72.44522

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS AND POLICY IMPLICATIONS

Empirical results from the recursive SVAR model present a consistent and coherent portrayal of short-run macroeconomic interdependence in an open economy context. By imposing *EXPORT* ordering this contemporaneous exogeneity, *FX* and *TAX* can be then considered endogenous, is guaranteed, and it leads to a simple hierarchical structure with propagating shocks from *EXPORT* to *FX*, *CPI*, and *TAX*. The significant own-shock coefficient on *EXPORT* confirms that the export innovations, which uncover are structurally uncorrelated and properly normalized under the chosen normalization, lending support to our interpretation of export shocks as exogenous drivers of domestic fluctuations.

Contemporaneous estimates suggest that positive export shocks would increase *FX* and reduce *CPI* in the same period but have no immediate effect on *TAX*. The fact that *FX* exhibits a positive response highlights the sensibility of exchange rates to trade-induced perturbations, supporting claims that external demand (or uncertainty) shocks are swiftly transmitted into currency markets. The negative effect of *EXPORT* and *FX* on *CPI* indicates that price responses in the short run depend more on external demand and cost channels than simple through-the-cycle movements in nominal exchange rates. The greater size of the export coefficient in the *CPI* equation reveals the power of real trade conditions rather than purely nominal channels to account for short-run inflation responses.

Fiscal dynamics have a more exogenous nature. *TAX* does not contemporaneously respond to export innovations, but it significantly reacts to *FX* and particularly *CPI* shocks. The significant and negative the coefficient implies that timing effects around the payment of taxes driven by inflation-related mechanisms, collection lag and real erosion of liabilities are a key driver of short-run revenue dynamics. Tax structural shocks remain significant, especially in the short run, as shown by variance decomposition results.

Both impulse responses and variance decompositions taken together make it evident that there is strong own-shock persistence within variables, while cross-variable effects are relatively more important at longer horizons. Taken together,

the results are consistent with an adjustment mechanism in which external shocks drive macroeconomic developments that first propagate through exchange rates and prices before reaching fiscal outcomes thus highlighting the central role of external sector innovations on short-run fluctuations in the economy.

The policy implications are that macroeconomic stabilization in the open economy should focus on external shocks resilience and transmission-management in both exchange rates, prices and fiscal channels. Because of the upstream drivers played by export, shocks on the short-run dynamics policy frameworks must also include active monitoring of global demand conditions, changes in trade policies, and measures of external uncertainty. Early-warning indicators that are based on trade or foreign business-cycle linkages would improve the readiness for spillovers to exchange rates and domestic prices.

Since *FX* does react substantially and swiftly to export innovations, one should try to minimize exchange rate management, along lines of flexibility combined with creating limits on volatility. A reliable monetary policy framework that is clearly committed to the maintenance of price stability, backstopped by sufficient foreign reserve buffers and macro prudential surveillance, would dampen disruptive currency adjustments induced by external shocks. However, if the data suggest that price dynamics are more sensitive to real trade conditions than to nominal exchange-rate pass-through, inflation-targeting policies should focus on demand cycles in trading partners and supply-side developments, instead of merely taking into account movements.

The strong contemporaneous influence of *CPI* on tax revenue also illustrates how fiscal outcomes are susceptible to distortions that arise from inflation. Efforts to strengthen tax administration by increasing collection efficiency and indexing wherever possible, while shortening the period required for settlements, would reduce cuts in real revenue during inflation. The portion of the nominal level of taxes that is sensitive to short-run fluctuations should also be diminished by strengthening automatic stabilizers and/or broadening the tax base. As tax specific shocks account for a sizeable portion of fiscal instability in the short run, reforms to institutions that enhance transparency and enforcement would

stabilize revenue performance.

For longer horizons, the increasing role of cross-variable effects points towards a need for policy coordination. It is recommended that an integrated framework to be employed by the monetary, exchange-rate and fiscal authorities should also take into account a sequence from exports having their

implications for macroeconomic aggregates. A policy mix which includes external sector competitiveness, exchange rate flexibility, price stability and strong fiscal institutions would improve macroeconomic resilience and minimize vulnerability to externally-induced shocks.

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